

LENGTH-SCALE-DEPENDANT STRENGTHENING OF PARTICLE-REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH STRAIN-GRADIENT PLASTICITY

Y. S. Suh^{1*}, M. S. Park¹, S. Song²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Hannam University, Daejeon, Korea, ² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Graduate School, Hannam University, Daejeon, Korea

* Corresponding author (suhy@hannam.kr)

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1 Introduction

Particle-reinforced metal matrix composites exhibits length scale in strength: smaller particle leads to higher strength for the same particle volume. This is usually distinct with the higher particle volume fraction. Arsenault and Shi [1], Lloyd [2], and Nan and Clarke [3] attributed such feature to the additional dislocation density that is necessary to accommodate large thermal misfit strains between the particles and the matrix. This additional geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density over and above the preexisting statistically stored dislocation density is believed to cause the increased yield strength of the composite as presented numerically by Qu et al. [4]. More recently, Suh et al. [5] demonstrated the length scale of the strength of particle-reinforced composites with an augmented unit-cell axisymmetric finite element model in such a way that the punched zone is represented as a fixed fraction of the matrix endowed with higher strength (due to the GNDs) than the rest of the matrix. Following Suh et al. [5], Shao et al. [6] showed similar strengthening effect using the Taylor-based nonlocal theory of plasticity in addition to punched zone modeling. Taupin et al. [7] also proposed a new mean field approach including an internal length scale in order to capture the particle size effects on the overall mechanical behavior of particle-reinforced alloys. They employed a generalized self-consistent scheme (with coated particles), with a new “phase” representing the “layers” where orderly dislocations between the matrix and the particles are present. The thickness of these “layers” is the internal length scale introduced in the model, which

is also a similar concept as the punched zone modeling proposed by Suh et al. [5].

Punched zone modeling, however, has some limitations: first, the accurate determination of punched zone size around the complex particle geometry is not easy (only applicable for simple geometries such as a sphere) or, in most cases, impossible. Second, it is only good for the regularly arranged particles. If the particles are clustered and the plastic deformation around a particle touches that of neighbor unit cell, the calculated punched zone size will not be applicable. In this work, we have implemented strain gradient plasticity into Abaqus UHARD and URDFIL to carry out a finite-element analysis on length-scale-dependent strengthening of particle-reinforced metal matrix composite. We included cooling (quench hardening) as a first stage in order to take account of length scale effect due to dislocation punching. This makes the modeling of enhanced strength zone unnecessary and therefore provides the greater freedom of taking various shape and arrangement of particles in the strength analysis. Further strengthening due to elastic-plastic mismatch is predicted by the strain gradient plasticity. Qu et al. [4] also included quench hardening at the initial stage but they added the enhanced strength due to thermal mismatch uniformly throughout the matrix, which is not appropriate since the dislocation punching due to thermal mismatch takes place along or near the particle – matrix interface as shown by Suh et al. [5].

2 Theoretical Background and Modeling

Taylor dislocation model for normal yield stress is expressed as following [8]:

$$\sigma = \alpha m G b \sqrt{\rho_{ssd} + \rho_{gnd}} \quad (1)$$

Where, ρ_{ssd} and ρ_{gnd} are statistically stored dislocation (SSD) density and geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density, respectively. m , G , b are Taylor factor, shear modulus of elasticity, magnitude of Burgers vector, respectively, and α is an empirical coefficient of order of magnitude of one. In case of uniaxial tensile test, GND becomes zero ($\rho_{gnd} = 0$) and the stress-strain relation can be expressed as $\sigma = \sigma_u(\varepsilon_p)$. Then SSD density becomes $\rho_{ssd} = (\sigma_u / \alpha m G b)^2$. On the other hand, GND density can be expressed as $\rho_{gnd} = \bar{r} \eta / b$ where \bar{r} is the Nye factor and η is the plastic strain gradient. So the equation (1) can be expressed as

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma_u^2 + (m\alpha G)^2 \bar{r} b \eta} \quad (2)$$

Note that the hardening equation (2) is dependent on the plastic strain gradient as well as plastic strain. The plastic strain gradient is expressed as following [8]:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\eta'_{ijk} \eta'_{ijk}} \quad (3)$$

where η'_{ijk} is the deviatoric strain gradient tensor of $\eta'_{ijk} = \eta_{ijk} - \frac{1}{4}(\delta_{ik}\eta_{jpp} + \delta_{jk}\eta_{ipp})$ but incompressibility of plastic deformation ($\varepsilon_{kk}^p = 0$) gives $\eta'_{ijk} = \eta_{ijk}$ and the plastic strain gradient tensor is the following equation.

$$\eta_{ijk} = \eta_{jik} \equiv u_{k,i,j} = \varepsilon_{ki,j}^p + \varepsilon_{kj,i}^p - \varepsilon_{ij,k}^p \quad (4)$$

For computation, Abaqus v. 6.9 was used with the user program UHARD for the equation (2) and URDFIL for the equation (3) and (4). Plastic strain gradient with the low order elements is evaluated by using an isoparametric interpolation of averaged-at-nodal plastic strain. A quarter of an axisymmetric unit cell was modeled. A uniform upward displacement is prescribed along the top boundary, while the right boundary remains traction-free and straight during deformation. The composite true

stress – true strain behavior of the unit-cell is obtained from the extensional displacement and the tensile force generated on the top boundary. After the entire cell had been cooled down by 474°C, upward displacement was applied. The mechanical properties for the matrix A356-T6 and the particle SiC were taken from Qu et al. [2] and Suh et al. [3].

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Spherical particulate composites

The predicted composite true stress – true strain curves with spherical particle are presented in Fig. 1. The predicted responses show distinct length scale depending on the particle size. As observed in the previous works [2, 3], SiC_p/A356 composites may have interfacial failure at larger strains. Since the present model was assumed to have perfectly bonded interface, the discrepancy at larger strains are not of concern. Strain gradient distributions immediately after the cooling and at the straining of 0.015 are shown in Fig. 2. It is noted that the strain gradient after cooling (which can be related to the GND) is higher with larger strain and smaller particle size, yielding more distinct size effect. Present results along with Suh et al.'s [3] clearly indicate that the strain gradient distribution after cooling is closely relevant with the dislocation punching zone.

Fig. 1. Comparison of numerical and experimental [5] composite true stress–strain curves for 2, 7.5 and 16 μm diameter SiC particles at 15% volume fraction.

Fig. 2. Strain gradient distributions immediately after the cooling (a, c) and at the strain of 0.015 (b, d). (a) and (b) are for 7.5 μm and (c) and (d) for 16 μm diameter particles. Note that the maximum strain gradient are generally shown near the interface in the direction of 45 degree from the horizontal axis.

This infers that modeling the punching zone in the unit cell is not necessary, allowing taking more complex particle geometry or particles with sharp corners (in whisker composites, for example) - calculating punch zone sizes for these cases are almost impossible – into finite-element analysis with a reasonable accuracy.

3.2 Whisker composites

The geometric configurations for ellipsoidal and cylindrical whisker composites are presented in Fig. 3. The influence of whisker shape on the composites strength is considered for different aspect ratio (AR) by changing r_0 . By varying aspect ratio with a fixed volume fraction of 20%, normalized composite yield stress (0.2% offset yield stress divided by the matrix offset yield stress) for ellipsoidal and cylindrical particulate composites are shown in Fig. 4. In comparison with classical approach (without cooling and strain gradient plasticity) as shown by Li and Ramesh [9], for example, the strengths are greater for all the aspect ratios, for both geometries.

Composite true stress - true strain curves are shown in Fig. 5 for ellipsoidal and cylindrical particulate composites for the aspect ratio of 5 with different particle size represented by r_0 . As with the spherical particles, the length scale associated with particle size are clearly observed. The yield stress and work hardening is larger for smaller particle size. This is more obvious with cylindrical than with ellipsoidal whisker which does not have sharp corners.

Fig. 3. Geometric configuration of axisymmetric unit cell for ellipsoidal and cylindrical particulate metal matrix composite.

Fig. 4. Composite normalized yield stress (0.2% offset yield stress divided by the matrix offset yield stress) for ellipsoidal and cylindrical particulate composites with various aspect ratio. Solid and dotted lines indicate the stress predicted by present and classical approach, respectively.

Fig. 5 Composite true stress - true strain for ellipsoidal and cylindrical particulate composites for the aspect ratio of 5 with different particle size represented by r_0 .

The strain gradient with ellipsoidal and cylindrical particulate composite at true strain of 0.02 for $r_0 = 2.5, 5$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$, are shown in Fig. 6 and 7, respectively. As for ellipsoidal whiskers, the strain gradient is higher near top where combined tensile and shear deformation is taking place. It is noted that the magnitude of strain gradient is higher and more dominating as the whisker size is decreased.

Fig. 6 Strain gradient for ellipsoidal particulate composite at true strain 0.02. (a) $r_0 = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (b) $r_0 = 5 \mu\text{m}$, and (c) $r_0 = 10 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 7 Strain gradient for cylindrical particulate composite at true strain 0.02. (a) $r_0 = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (b) $r_0 = 5 \mu\text{m}$, and (c) $r_0 = 10 \mu\text{m}$.

Similar results are observed for cylindrical whiskers. Not only the shape, but also the arrangements of whiskers are strongly influence the strengthening of the composites. The punch modeling proposed by Qu et al. [4], Suh et al. [5], and Shao et al. [6] cannot predict the strength correctly as the distance between the whiskers is too close, when the analytical determination of punch size is no longer valid. With the present approach including pre-cooling calculation and strain gradient plasticity, the length-dependent strength for any type of whisker arrangement can be effectively and correctly predicted. Llorca et al. [10] have predicted the strength of whisker-reinforced metal matrix composites for various whisker shape and arrangement. In this work, the size effect by different whisker arrangements are considered following Llorca et al.'s configuration, where the horizontal and vertical degree of clustering are expressed by the shortened distance between whiskers in respective direction. Assuming plane strain, the composite strength for uniform, 50% of horizontal and vertical degrees of clustering are compared in Fig. 9. Once the distance between whiskers are shortened either horizontally or vertically, the strength are thought to be decreased since the dislocation punch zone of each whisker is collided. In Fig. 9, in terms of strength decrease, it is observed that the clustering is more influential with

the vertical direction than horizontal, since a localization of strain along a diagonal band is formed between the top and bottom corners for former case as shown in Fig. 10. Therefore, for a fixed 50% of vertical degree of clustering, aspect ratio to be 5 and at a 20% of volume fraction, the length scale dependency on the composite strength is examined. The true stress - true strain of cylindrical whisker composites with different size (represented by r_0) of particles are displayed in Fig. 11, where a strong size dependency is observed. This is explained by Figs. 12 and 13 where effective plastic strain and strain gradient of the cylindrical whisker

Fig. 9 True stress - true strain of cylindrical whisker composites with different arrangement of particles.

Fig. 10 Effective plastic strain of cylindrical whisker composite with different arrangements at true strain 0.02. (a) Uniform distribution (b) 50% horizontal clustering, and (c) 50% vertical clustering.

Fig. 11 True stress - true strain of cylindrical whisker composites with different size (represented by r_0) of particles.

composite with different sizes (represented by r_0) at true strain 0.02. Especially in Fig. 13, the higher strain gradient at the end of neighboring whiskers is shown for the smaller size.

4 Conclusion

The length-scale dependent strength of particle or whisker reinforced metal matrix composites is predicted by the displacement based low order finite element method with strain gradient plasticity. For this, strain gradient hardening with single length parameter was implemented to Abaqus user subroutines UHARD and URDFIL. Initially the cooling (quench hardening) is included in order to take account of length scale effect due to dislocation punching. This makes the modeling of enhanced strength zone unnecessary and therefore provides the greater freedom of taking various shape and arrangement of particles in the strength analysis. Further strengthening due to elastic-plastic mismatch is predicted by the strain gradient plasticity. The predicted and experimental composite true stress – true strain curves for spherical particle revealed distinct length scale depending on the particle size with reasonable accuracy. Further results with ellipsoidal and cylindrical shape and different arrangement of whiskers showed clear size effect

Fig. 12 Effective plastic strain of cylindrical whisker composite with different sizes (represented by r_0) at a true strain value of 0.02. (a) $r_0 = 1 \mu\text{m}$ (b) $r_0 = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, and (c) $r_0 = 5 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 13 Strain gradient of cylindrical whisker composite with different sizes (represented by r_0) at a true strain value of 0.02. (a) $r_0 = 1 \mu\text{m}$ (b) $r_0 = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, and (c) $r_0 = 5 \mu\text{m}$.

on the strength which cannot be achieved with the previous approach such as punch zone modeling [4-6]. Further work will include the interfacial decohesion between particle and matrix and ductile failure due to void nucleation and growth in the matrix, in order to examine the size dependency of failure behavior.

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